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FOOD SECURITY IN AFRICA

BEZPIECZEŃSTWO ŻYWNOŚCIOWE W AFRYCE

MSc thesis

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this thesis is to evaluate the level of food security in Sub-Saharan Africa and to ascertain the individual and household dietary intake in the region. The procedure includes using the Food Insecurity Experience Scale (FIES) to learn the level of food insecurity in SSA households and individuals. The data were collected via the distribution of electronic questionnaires.

A total of 100 adults completed the online survey, 79% were male and 21% female, their age bracket was between 20-70 years, and the majority of those who responded were from Nigeria, Ghana, Cameroun, and the Ivory Coast.

The study suggests that the proper management of the SSA economy and massive investment in the Agricultural sector may contribute to the increase in the level of food security in the SSA countries.

STRESZCZENIE

Celem pracy jest ocena poziomu bezpieczeństwa żywnościowego w Afryce Subsaharyjskiej oraz ustalenie spożycia indywidualnego i gospodarstw domowych w tym regionie. Procedura obejmuje użycie skali doświadczenia braku bezpieczeństwa żywności (FIES), w celu rozpoznania poziomu braku bezpieczeństwa żywnościowego w gospodarstwach domowych i indywidualnego w regionie Afryki Subsaharyjskiej. Dane zostały zebrane przy wykorzystaniu kwestionariusza elektronicznego .

W sumie ankietę internetową wypełniło 100 osób, spośród których 79% stanowili mężczyźni, a 21% kobiety. Ich przedział wiekowy wynosił od 20 do 70 lat, a większość osób, które odpowiedziały, pochodzi z Nigerii, Ghany, Kamerunu i Wybrzeża Kości Słoniowej.

Z badania wynika, że właściwe zarządzanie gospodarką SSA i duże inwestycje w sektorze rolnym zwiększyłyby poziom bezpieczeństwa żywnościowego w krajach SSA.

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INTRODUCTION

Food security is a critical element of the Sustainable Development Goals and government guidelines in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA). The expression “food security” was introduced in 1974 following famines inside the Sahel and Darfur (Gerlach, 2015), and was, first of all, focused on the production and availability of sufficient food. However, these and later African famines have been no longer because of unavailability or inadequate regional manufacturing of foods. Instead, they arose from governments’ failure to integrate and maintain track of rural meal production, storage, and distribution systems and Governments' inability or unwillingness to offer grain on time (de Waal, 2018; Lappé & Collins, 1982; Sen, 1981). Food security is, consequently, inextricably related to poverty, governments’ ability, and political willingness to mediate (Reutlinger and Selowsky, 1976).

The idea of food security now encompasses physical and economic access to sufficient, secure, and nutritious food, which meets dietary wishes and food options for an active and healthy life (FAO, 1996). However, many SSA families could not produce or purchase enough nutritious food. Access to meals across SSA made progress in the 1960s and 70s with the provision of US grain imports. However, the debt disaster and the International Monetary Fund’s (IMF) Structural Adjustment Policies (SAPs), imposed in the 80s and 90s, curtailed spending on imports, and the availability of food fell underneath tiers within the 1960s (Dietz, 2013). The situation has slowly stepped forward in view since 2000, but in 2016, 27% of the population lived with extreme food insecurity due to rising inequality and income disparity (Dietz, 2013; FAO, 2017). This affects more than 300 million people, with 240 million malnourished, mainly in rural households (FAO, 2017). A 5-fold boom in population on account of independence has exacerbated the trouble, leaving SSA four instances greater affected than any other vicinity and with food insecurity growing (FAO, 2017; van Bavel, 2013).

The purpose of the study is to assess the height of food security in the Sub-Saharan African countries (SSA) and to define the reasons why the SSA has not been food self-sufficient. The additional purpose of the study is to find out the dietary intakes of the SSA households and contribute to the food sufficient of the region.

The methodology used is from the Food and Agriculture Organization Food Insecurity Experience Scale (FIES) is an experience-based measure of household or individual food security. The FIES Survey Module consists of questions regarding people’s access to adequate food and can be

integrated into various types of population surveys. The method of data collection of the study is via the electronic form sent to households and individuals in the SSA

The first chapter focuses on the background of the study how food is generally viewed by researchers, the definition of food security, the assessment of food security, food insecurity and hunger, and the levels of food security. The second chapter talks about an overview of food security, food production, and consumption, characteristics of food security in Africa, factors of food insecurity, measurement of food security, level of food insecurity in SSA and the form of coping with food insecurity. The third emphasizes characteristics of food consumption, dietary food consumption, comparing different indicators of food security used in SSA and developed countries, income and expenditure and the socio-economic status as an indicator of food insecurity. The fourth chapter discussed the method used for the data collection, data research and analysis and the synthesis of the findings.

The material source of this research was derived from the Food and Agricultural Organization methods on household food experience scale, contribution from the world bank, Africa development bank, journals and scientific articles.

CHAPTER 1. BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

1.1 GENERAL VIEW OF FOOD

Food is among humans' basic needs for social development. Food can be seen as an element that humans and animals consume, that provides nutrients such as carbohydrates, fats, proteins, vitamins, and minerals for the body. It comes from either plant or animal sources. Food absorbed by the body helps to produce energy and stimulate healthy growth. It is important to note that food acts as a source of survival for human existence. Without food, man cannot survive and may easily be attacked by diseases that can be prevented by food intake (Okonkwo 2005).

Food security is a concern in Africa, with a large %age of the population experiencing food insecurity (Low or moderate food security), families go to bed without dinners, and homes are devastated due to food not being available for the children leading to stunted growth. The lack of complete food security in Africa demands urgent action, especially in light of the negative impact on both nutrient intake and body weight status. It is a severe public health problem.

1.2 Definition of Food Security

Food security is a measure of the availability of food and an individual's ability to access it. Thus, food security is not simply a matter of sufficient food supply but is also related to regional accessibility, the purchasing power of residents, food quality, political and socio-economic stability, and other factors (Xie 2004).

In a most recent UN summit in New York, the secretary general (Guterres 2021) described food security as having enough food to eat not just for today or tomorrow but also next month and all year round.

According to the Africa Development bank Chairperson (Akinwunmi 2017), food security is the right of every individual in Africa to enjoy a standard and nutritious three-square meal daily without difficulties affording it.

The American Nutrition and Dietetics defines food security as access to an adequate amount of safe nutrition, and culturally appropriate food always is a fundamental human right (Struble and Aomari 2003).

Dado (2020), in his article 'Understanding Africa's food security', defined food security as a condition in which all African people and the world at large, at all times, have physical and economic access to adequate, safe, and nutritious food, meeting their nutritional requirements and their food preferences for an active and balanced life.

The World Summit on Food Security, held in Rome in 1996, aimed to renew a global commitment to the fight against hunger (Maxwell, 1996). The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO UN 1975) called the summit in response to widespread under-nutrition and growing concern about the capacity of agriculture to meet future food needs. The conference produced two key documents, the Rome Declaration on World Food Security and the World Food Summit Plan of Action.

The Rome Declaration called for the members of the United Nations to work to halve the number of chronically undernourished people on the Earth by the year 2015. The Plan of Action establishes several goals for governments and non-governmental organizations to achieve food security on an individual, household, national, regional, and global scale (Hart 2009).

According to the United Nations Committee on World Food Security, food security means that all people constantly have physical, social, and economic access to sufficient safe and nutritious food that meets their food preferences and dietary needs for an active and healthy life.

Food insecurity has emerged as a global crisis and is a serious obstacle to sustainable development (Laborde, Martin, Vos 2020). The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) states that about 870 million people are undernourished worldwide, of which 30% are found in Sub-Saharan Africa (FAO, 2012). Africa has achieved success both economically and in agricultural production. According to the World Bank, its Gross National Income (GNI) in 2011 was estimated at 4820 US dollars per capita. Agricultural production has been on the decline due to several factors. At the regional level, there is not enough food available for the African population, estimated at more than 2098 calories per day in 2012. Despite some nutritionists' doubts, this measure is widely used by the World Bank, the FAO, and many food analysts.

Three types of food insecurity can also be distinguished by their frequency or duration (Gibson 2012, Obioma 2008):

- Chronic food insecurity: A persistent and long-term state of food insecurity: a population suffers from chronic food insecurity when it is unable to meet minimum food consumption requirements for extended periods of time (approximately six months of the year or longer).

- Temporary food insecurity - A short-term and temporary state of food insecurity: a population suffers from transitory food insecurity when there is a sudden drop in the ability to produce or access sufficient food for a healthy nutritional status (e.g., after a period of drought or because of conflict).
- Food insecurity during the season: a condition of food insecurity that reoccurs predictably, following the cyclical pattern of seasons.

The common short-run definition of food security in a single country or in the world is the ability of food-deficit countries, regions within countries, or households within these countries to meet target consumption levels on a year-to-year basis (Valdes, 1981, Bigman, 1985).

1.3 Assessment of Food Security

Assessment is a process that is used to understand a situation to make decisions on whether there is a need to respond to a hazard or to a situation that can lead to disaster if nothing is done. It also means judgment, appraisal, estimation, or evaluation. Food security assessments are no different from general assessments in their aim. Still, they look more specifically at how people and households try to maintain a secure food environment for themselves and whether they succeed. The general objective of a food security assessment is to understand how severe food insecurity is, and why this is the case. Then the objective is to determine if there is a need to intervene to return the people to a normal food security situation soon.

The focus of a security assessment will be on evaluating the food security of Sub-Saharan African countries. Furthermore, food security assessments can help to predict upcoming food insecurity or the duration of an insecure food period.

In food security assessment, there is a need to understand how people make their living, whether through food production or working for a salary, or both. Specifically, we need to know how they meet their needs. It is necessary to understand who can access these resources and whether this access changes over time. For example, it may be that water sources for animals are restricted in the dry season and only those who can pay to access them.

There are five commonly used methods that can be used to assess food security:

I. The Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) method for estimating calories available per capita at the national level:

II. Household income and expenditure surveys

III. Individual's dietary intake

IV. Anthropometry

V. Experience-based food insecurity measurement scales.

The FAO method estimates calories per capita at the country level using Food Balance Sheets and energy intake variance data derived from household income and expenditure surveys. Countries need the following information to be able to apply this method:

i) Total calories available in the year of interest

ii) Number of people living in regions in the year of interest;

iii) Coefficient of variation of caloric intake to generate the energy intake distribution curve;

iv) Cut-off point to estimate the proportion of the population falling under the minimum per capita average caloric requirement. (Figure 1)

Figure 1: Method Used For Assessing Food Security

Source: FAO

Household income and expenditure surveys

This method is based on interviewing respondents in their households. Respondents provide information on the amount of money they spend on food and other necessities. Different time reference periods have been used, including the week(s) or month(s) preceding the survey. The following inputs are needed to be able to take full advantage of this method:

- i) quantity of food bought (or expenditures) and costs associated with different foods consumed within and outside the house;
- ii) foods received by any household member as either a gift or as payment for work, goods, or services;
- iii) foods are grown for consumption by household members. This method estimates calories consumed on average per household member per day, making it essential to access culturally appropriate and valid food composition tables.

Individual's Dietary Intake

The individual's dietary intake can be measured through different methods, including:

- i) 24-hour recall;
- ii) food frequency questionnaires;
- iii) food records kept by individuals or by an observer. All dietary intake methods need to make use of a reference time frame.

Whereas some of the methods rely on participants' memory (24-hour recall, food frequency questionnaire), others rely on the recording of foods consumed by the study participant, a proxy, or an observer. Portion size estimations can rely on assisted memory (e.g., using food models), or foods can actually be weighed before and right after consumption. These portion size estimations are needed to estimate food group counts and nutrient intakes, provided that culturally appropriate and valid food composition databases are available. Lastly, to interpret the nutrient intake findings, it is important to have cut-off points for determining the proportion of the sample or population at risk of deficiencies in different nutrients.

Anthropometry

Anthropometry is defined as the measurement of size, weight, body proportions, and ultimately the composition of the human body. Anthropometric indicators measure the impact of both food

insecurity and health status on the nutritional status of individuals. The anthropometric indicators most commonly used in national surveys are based on the weight and height (or length) of infants, young children, youth, and adults. The interpretation of the adequacy of the anthropometric indicators is based on well-established cut-off points.

Food Insecurity Experience-Based Measurement Scales

All the methods discussed above are derived or indirect measurements of the phenomena of interest (i.e., food insecurity). Fortunately, over the past two decades, there have been major advances in the fundamental measurement of household food insecurity in the Sahara region, using scales based on the perception or experience reported by the affected individuals. The foundational work that led to this effort was conducted by Cornell and Tufts Universities researchers in the United States of America (USA) and by a non-governmental organization. Because the Cornell researchers fully documented the process, this section concentrates first on their work, followed by how the US Department of Agriculture coordinated the process that led to the US Household Food Security Survey Measure (HFSSM) based on the experience-based scales previously developed in the USA.

1.4 Food Insecurity and Hunger

Freedom from hunger has been described as a fundamental human right, which explains why eliminating hunger is one of the UN Millennium Development Goals (MDGs). In fact, attaining this goal will go a long way in facilitating the achievement of the other MDGs and may also reduce cultural war and conflict (UN Dept. of Economic and Social Affairs, 2004).

Other institutions have also developed indices that measure one or more aspects of food security at the country level. For example, the Global Hunger Index (GHI), developed by International Food Policy Research Institute (I.F.P.R.I), aims to measure “hunger” using three equally weighted indicators: (Connell & von Oppeln Co, 2013)

- (1) Undernourishment (i.e., the proportion of undernourished people as a %age of the population),
- (2) Child underweight (i.e., the proportion of children younger than 5 years who have a low weight for their age),

(3) Child mortality (i.e., the mortality rate for children younger than 5 years. Countries are ranked on a 100-point scale and categorized as having “low” to “extremely alarming” hunger.

Data for the child mortality and undernourishment components of the index come from UNICEF and the FAO, respectively. The underweight child component of the index comes from 3 sources: the WHO Global Database on Child Growth and Malnutrition, Demographic and Health Survey data, and UNICEF's Multiple Indicator Cluster Survey reports. (Global Nutrition Report, 2021).

The stated purpose of the index is to highlight successes and failures in hunger reduction” and raise awareness and understanding of regional and country differences in hunger.” The term “hunger” as used here ostensibly represents a manifestation of severe food insecurity. However, the component measurements of the GHI also reflect child health and under-nutrition, the determinants of which are not necessarily associated with food insecurity (e.g., access to health services, household water, sanitation environments, care for women and children). The interpretation of the GHI as a measure of food security or hunger becomes complicated by this additional information captured by the index.

Food insecurity and hunger are caused by many factors, often intertwined with one another. In general, the principal causes of hunger include poverty, conflict, climate and weather, lack of investment in agriculture, and unstable markets (World Food Programme, 2018).

Poverty is a principal cause of hunger in Africa and elsewhere. Individuals living in poverty often cannot afford food of sufficient quality or quantity to live a healthy life. According to the World Bank, in 2013, 42.3% of the population of Sub-Saharan Africa lived on \$1.90 or less per day, a principal factor of widespread hunger. Poverty is often a cycle. Children exposed to long-term undernutrition are often stunted, leading to long-term consequences, including decreased labor productivity and income-earning potential (FAO, 2017).

Also, conflict and violence can have direct and indirect impacts on all food system levels, leading to food insecurity and hunger. Conflict often puts constraints on employment and income opportunities, which affects an individual’s ability to acquire food. Conflict can also affect exports and imports, which can lead to limited food availability and affordability. Food availability can also be affected if resources (land, equipment, etc.) used to produce food are destroyed during times of conflict (FAO, 2017).

In 2017, conflict was the major cause of food insecurity and hunger in 18 countries, affecting about 74 million individuals (almost twice the population of Poland). Eleven of these countries were in

Africa, which totaled about 37 million people (nearly the population of Poland). Northern Nigeria, the Democratic Republic of Congo, Somalia, and South Sudan account for the majority of these individuals (Food Security Information Network, 2018). Since 2013, South Sudan has experienced ongoing conflict, which has caused an increase in food insecurity. In 2017, parts of South Sudan declared famine, and more than 42% of the population faced severe food insecurity (FAO, 2017).

Another factor is the environment. Environmental challenges, including erosion, desertification, deforestation, drought, and water shortages, can harm food security. In 2017, 23 countries experienced food crises due to climate and weather conditions. Two-thirds of these countries were in Africa, affecting approximately 32 million people.

As stated above, the causes of hunger are often intertwined. For example, in 2017, Uganda faced food insecurity due to a drought that occurred in 2016. During this period, Uganda was already experiencing food insecurity due to an influx of refugees (Food Security Information Network, 2018). The environmental challenges from drought increased poverty and hunger by reducing agricultural production and people's incomes.

Many of these challenges are man-made. Deforestation, for example, is caused by humans seeking new places to live, farm, or obtain firewood. Drought, water shortage, and desertification in Africa all reduce agricultural productivity and thus food availability.

As mentioned above, there is a clear connection between conflict and hunger, but poor governance and policies also lead to hunger due to insufficient access to food.

Many countries have seen progress in reducing hunger among their citizens after implementing policies that increase food security. For example, in the early 2000s, Ethiopia invested in agricultural research and extension, leading to increases in food availability. This increased investment in infrastructure helped move crops to markets, increasing food access (IFPRI, 2017). Consuming poor-quality food can lead to malnutrition. Policies such as food fortification programs can increase the availability of nutritious foods. Implementing iodine fortification programs in Kenya, Rwanda, Tanzania, and Zimbabwe have been successful (Mijumbi, 2011).

One must consider that Africa's population increased rapidly, from 221 million in 1950 to 1.2 billion in 2018. Africa experiences the highest population growth rate among world regions; between 2010 and 2015, it grew at a rate of 2.55% per year. It is estimated that more than half of the global population growth between now and 2050 will occur in Africa (United Nations, 2018). Rapid population growth can limit increases in per capita income, causing poverty and hunger.

1.5 Levels of food security

The world health organization (WHO) states that there are three pillars that determine food security: food availability, food access, and food use and misuse. The FAO adds a fourth pillar: the stability of the first three dimensions of food security over time. In 2009, the World Summit on Food Security stated that the "four levels of food security are, Availability, Access, Utilization, and Stability (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Pillars of Food Security

Source: 2020 Global Programme Food Security

As it pertains to the delivery of food through production, distribution, and exchange. Food manufacturing is decided by way of many elements, together with land possession and utilization; management of soil; crop choice, breeding, and management, animal breeding and control; and harvesting. Crop manufacturing may be affected by modifications in the quantity of rainfall and temperatures. The use of land, water, and strength use to develop food regularly competes with

different uses, that could affect food production. Land used for agricultural functions can be used for urbanization or misplaced to desertification, salinization, and soil erosion because of a lack of sustainable agricultural practices. Crop production isn't always required for a rustic to reap meals security. Countries do not should have the herbal assets required to provide vegetation to gain food safety, as seen inside the examples of Asian countries like Japan and Singapore

Because food consumers are more than producers in every country, food must be distributed to different regions or nations. Food distribution involves the storage, processing, transporting, packaging, and marketing of food. Food chain infrastructure and storage technologies on farms can also affect the amount of food wasted in the distribution process. Poor transport infrastructure can increase the price of supplying water and fertilizer as well as the price of moving food to national and global markets. Around the world, few individuals or families are continuously self-reliant on food. This brings the need for a bartering, exchange, or cash economy to acquire food. The exchange of food requires efficient trading systems and market institutions, which can affect food security. Per capita, world food supplies are more than adequate to provide food security to all, and thus, food accessibility is a greater barrier to achieving food security. (Global Food Security, 2021)

Access to livestock such as goats is an important part of the solution to global food security because they cost less to maintain and are easy to raise and farm.

Food access refers to the affordability and distribution of food, as well as the choices of individuals and households. The UN Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights stated that the causes of hunger and malnutrition are often not a scarcity of food but an inability to access available food, usually due to poverty. Poverty can limit access to food and can also increase how vulnerable an individual or family is to food price spikes. Access depends on whether the family has enough income to purchase food at prevailing prices or has sufficient land and other resources to grow its own food. Families with enough resources can overcome unstable harvests and local food shortages and maintain their access to food.

There are two distinct types of access to food: direct access, in which a household produces food using human and material resources, and economic access, in which a household purchases food produced elsewhere. Location can affect food access and the type of access a family will rely on. A household's assets, including income, land products of labor, inheritances, and gifts, can determine a household's access to food. However, the ability to access sufficient food may not

lead to the purchase of food over other materials and services. The demographics and education levels of the household members, as well as the gender of the household head, determine the preferences of the household, which influence the type of food purchased. A household's access to adequate and nutritious food may not assure enough food intake for all household members, as intra-household food allocation may not sufficiently meet the requirements of each member of the household. The USDA adds that access to food must be available in socially acceptable ways without, for example, resorting to emergency food supplies, scavenging, stealing, or other coping strategies.

The next pillar of food security is food utilization, which refers to the metabolism of food by individuals. Once a household obtains the food, a variety of factors affect the quantity and quality of food that reaches members of the household. To achieve food security, the food consumed must be safe and must be adequate to meet the physiological requirements of everyone. Food safety affects food utilization, and can be affected by the preparation, processing, and cooking of food in the community and household. Nutritional values of the household determine food preference and whether food meets cultural preferences is important to utilization in terms of psychological and social well-being. Access to healthcare is another determinant of food utilization, since the health of individuals controls how the food is metabolized. For example, intestinal parasites can take nutrients from the body and decrease food utilization. Sanitation can also decrease the occurrence and spread of diseases affecting food utilization. Education about nutrition and food preparation can affect food utilization and improve this pillar of food security (USAID 1995).

Another level of food security is food stability, which refers to the ability to obtain food over time. Food insecurity can be transitory, seasonal, or chronic. In transitory food insecurity, food may be unavailable during certain periods of time. At the food production level, drought results in crop failure and decreased food availability. Civil conflicts can also decrease access to food. Instability in markets resulting in food-price spikes can cause transitory food insecurity. Other factors that can temporarily cause food insecurity are loss of employment or productivity, which can be caused by illness. Seasonal food insecurity can result from the regular pattern of growing seasons in food production.

Chronic (or permanent) food insecurity is defined as the long-term, persistent lack of adequate food. In this case, households are constantly at risk of being unable to acquire food to meet the

needs of all members. Chronic and transitory food insecurity are linked since the reoccurrence of transitory food security can make families more vulnerable to chronic food insecurity.

CHAPTER 2: AN OVERVIEW OF FOOD SECURITY IN AFRICA

Food security in sub-Saharan Africa remains a major developmental challenge, despite several interventions to improve food security and nutrition in many developing regions. Recent official estimates suggest that hunger and malnutrition appear to be increasing in most sub-Saharan African countries, a situation that is in contrast to the rest of the world (FAO, ECA, and AUC 2020). The increasing food insecurity in Africa, combined with the fact that persistent food insecurity, contributed to the failure of countries in the region in meeting the Millennium Development Goal (MDG) of halving the number of hungry people by 2015 (Abdulai and Kuhlitz 2012), suggest the need for continuous efforts in supporting and promoting measures to improve food security in the region. While the worsening food situation can partly be attributed to climate change (Abdulai 2018; FAO, ECA, and AUC 2020), as well as poor and weakening market conditions, the impact of agricultural markets on food security and nutrition appears to be far from being conclusive (Carletto, Corral, and Guelfi 2017; Linderhof, Janssen, and Achterbosch 2019; Ehui 2020).

Africa is not on track to meet the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG2) targets to end hunger and ensure access by all people to safe, nutritious, and sufficient food all year round and end all forms of malnutrition. The most recent estimates show that 281.6 million people on the continent, over one-fifth of the population, faced hunger in 2020, which is 46.3 million more than in 2019. This deterioration continues a trend that started in 2014, after a prolonged period of improving food security. In addition to hunger, millions of Africans suffer from widespread micronutrient deficiencies, and progress towards achieving the global nutrition targets by 2030 remains unacceptably (ARFSD 2021).

2.1 Food Production and Consumption

Food consumption expressed in kilocalories (kcal) per capita per day is a key variable used for measuring and evaluating the evolution of the global and regional food situation (FAO, 2003). A more appropriate term for this variable would be “national average apparent food consumption” since the data come from national Food Balance Sheets rather than from food consumption surveys. Analysis of FAOSTAT data (see table 3) that dietary energy measured in kcals per capita

per day, henceforth food consumption, has been increasing in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA). However, food consumption has not been steadily increasing. In the period between 1981 and 1991, consumption decreased in SSA, and this decrease could be attributed to the continent-wide economic crisis that economists call the lost decade of Africa (Nicolas Bricas 2014; Claude Tchamda 2016)

The market plays a dominant role in food consumption in both urban and rural areas. Depending on the country, food purchases amount to between two-thirds and nine-tenths of national consumption. The share of purchased food is very high in cities, amounting to more than 80% of food value in secondary cities and more than 90% of food value in capitals or major cities. Even more surprising is the dominance of market supply in food consumption in rural areas. Self-agricultural production accounts for less than half of the economic value of food consumed. Quite far, indeed, from the past when rural diets were essentially provided for by subsistence agriculture. The food system has become almost completely monetized. As a result, urban and rural households alike have now become sensitive to fluctuations in food prices, and not only to the amount of food they produce, but for their own supply. Such a situation can be explained by two phenomena. First, (i) rural areas are not just inhabited by farmers and their families: they also include small towns (in Nigeria, for example, populations in centres of up to 20,000 inhabitants are classified as rural) where the range of jobs is thus not restricted to agriculture people work at jobs such as small-scale food processing, artisanal construction, repair and maintenance, trade, transport, education, health services and the like and they buy their food at markets. Second, (ii) farmers sell part of their production either within the country or for export. Income also circulates through remittances by family members living in the city or abroad (Losch et al., 2012). People in rural areas combine their various sources of income to purchase a significant part of their household food supply. Such trends in rural food supply chains have a non-negligible impact on food security because even though people in rural areas have more opportunities than city dwellers to grow their own crops, they are also more vulnerable to food price changes. Food security can be affected if increases in the cost of food are greater than increases in the income earned from production. Rural citizens are more at risk because their budgets tend to be modest. As a result, issues with food security in rural and urban areas tend to converge with the increasing importance of food markets and food prices. By converting the value of the domestic market to dollars according to the average rate of currency for the year of the study, comparisons can be made with export markets for agricultural products.

In terms of economic value, meeting domestic market demand is much more lucrative than exporting food products for every country studied, including for major agricultural exporters such as Ivory Coast and Cameroon (see table 1).

Table 1: Export Value of Agricultural Produce

Cameroon	Export Value of Bananas		
Year	Belgium	France	Germany
2011	12894	39360	724
2012	11998	38062	448
2014	21015	27954	3
2015	19525	16941	545
2016	19290	18881	15
2017	27989	13354	
2018	31681	11015	
2019	127181	14900	
2020	137460	16428	

Source: FAOSTAT

Table 2: Export Value of Coco beans

Ivory Coast	Export value of Coco beans			
Year	Belgium	France	Germany	Netherlands
2011	225243	89044	243426	836760
2012	269515	41431	191899	506710
2013	260473	99063	161699	389775
2014	415193	55428	203777	614534
2015	624168	94993	311354	839175
2016	508113	87608	290861	698978
2017	439466	119939	316939	784237
2018	264049	101049	298939	850341
2019	396999	116547	299471	875644
2020	393765	128774	338917	1117853

Source: FAOSTAT

Food consumption issues cannot be exclusively focused on grains and cereal. Economic values of food products destined for household consumption can be classified into three wide categories: The first consists of starchy staples, which provide a significant portion of the energy intake: grains

and cereals (millet, sorghum, maize, rice, wheat, folio), roots (cassava, taro, cocoyam), tubers (yam, sweet potatoes, potatoes) and plantain banana. At a national level, these products make up between 40% and 50% of the economic value of food consumption (see figure 3).

The second consists of animal products: meat, fish and seafood, dairy, and eggs. The consumption of these products represents between 15% and 30% of the economic value of food consumption, depending on the country.

The third consists of “other” products, such as sauce-related products (vegetables, oils, pulses, and nuts) and sweet products (sugar, fruits, and non-alcoholic beverages), as well as products that are bought out of home but consumed at home. Consumption of such food products amounts to between 30% and 40% of the total. The following food, fruits, and vegetable data was available in FAO cassava, coco bean, banana, cashew nutshell, ginger, and garlic

Coco bean - The West African countries of Ghana, Côte d'Ivoire, Nigeria, and Cameroon produce nearly 70 % of the world's cocoa. Côte d'Ivoire alone accounts for 40 % of global cocoa production.

Figure 2: Value of Agricultural Production(2011-2020)

Source: FAO

Cassava Production-also, known as *Manihot esculenta*, is majorly produced in Sub-Saharan Africa, and almost all the countries produce cassava as a staple food. The crop is now produced in 40 of the 53 countries of SSA, accounting for 61% of global production. And presently, Nigeria, Ghana, Ivory Coast, and Malawi are the largest cassava producers in the Sahel region (figure 4).

Figure 3. Cassava production (2011-2020)

Source: FAO

Banana – It is widely grown in Africa because of the fertile soil. It has a nutritional value and in the Sub-Sahara Africa Cameroon, Ivory cost and Malawi are the highest producers of tropical fruit.

Figure 4:Banana Production(2011-2020)

Source: FAO.

Cashew nutshell - Cashews thrive in the tropical climates of 20 western and eastern African nations, where about 90% of the raw cashew nuts traded in the global market are grown. Behind

Côte d'Ivoire, the main producers are Tanzania, Nigeria, Benin, Guinea-Bissau, Mozambique, and Ghana (figure 6)

Figure 5:Cashew Nut Production (2011-2020)

Source: FAO.

Ginger plant - Nigeria was the main producer of ginger in Africa as of 2020. The country produced this flowering plant in the amount of over 734,000 metric tons. Cameroon and Mali followed with a production volume reaching 65,453 metric tons and 34,861 metric tons, respectively.

Figure 6:Ginger Production (2011-2020)

Source: FAOSTAT.

Food Consumption In Sub-Saharan Africa

We approximated meals intake underneath by means of subtracting food exports from the sum of food production, food imports, and meals aid. In discern underneath we present consistent with capita food intake in SSA.

Figure 7 SSA Per capita Consumption Food

Source: author’s own estimation based on FAO.

Average per capita food consumption ranges between 0.7 and 0.8 tons of food per year. Recently, it decreased to less than 0.7 tons. This is because the population has been growing at a faster rate compared to food production. Food consumption in SSA has recently been supported by imported food. It was discovered that the average growth rate of imported food to be five percent while the average growth rate in food production and food export to be two and one percent, respectively. Without food imports, SSA per capita consumption would have been about four percent (FAO, 2003)

Food Consumption in Individual SSA Countries

Food consumption expressed in kilocalories (kcal) per capita per day is a key variable used for measuring and evaluating the evolution of the global and regional food situation (FAO, 2003). A more appropriate term for this variable would be “national average apparent food consumption” since the data come from national Food Balance Sheets rather than from food consumption

surveys. Analysis of FAOSTAT data shows that dietary energy measured in kcals per capita per day, henceforth food consumption, has been increasing in SSA. However, food consumption has not been steadily increasing. Between 1981 and 1991, consumption decreased in SSA, which could be attributed to the continent-wide economic crisis that economists call the lost decade of Africa.

Table 3: Total Food Consumption (Kcal/per/day)

Location	1961-1971	1971-1981	1981-1991	1991-2001	2001-2007
SSA	2201.32	2210.82	2206.72	2236.89	2310.26
Cote d'Ivoire	2557.44	2696.73	2605.80	2433.52	2493.21
DRC	2282.81	2219.92	2186.48	1788.65	1570.95
Ethiopia	1748.97	1603.88	1626.74	1670.10	1915.49
Ghana	2102.13	1933.96	1927.43	2483.26	2783.98
Kenya	2291.84	2334.55	2129.8z8	2026.83	2033.87
Nigeria	1900.89	1779.06	1961.11	2532.21	2638.89
South Africa	2748.51	2858.69	2860.49	2838.27	2957.96
Tanzania	1733.24	2087.46	2212.02	1965.95	1981.46
Benin	1909.03	1920.56	2054.03	2319.10	2479.38
Burkina Faso	1710.69	1690.92	2113.60	2522.72	2646.42
Burundi	2115.15	2057.77	1892.61	1716.07	1685.40
Cameroon	2055.67	2238.91	2040.74	2060.59	2240.88
Gambia	2390.06	1934.87	2373.52	2283.54	2302.15
Guinea Bissau	1783.83	1913.37	2203.48	2219.08	2251.50
Madagascar	2519.67	2545.81	2350.91	2103.93	2092.43
Malawi	2209.19	2345.11	2036.57	1981.62	2094.39
Mali	1692.84	1617.23	1992.26	2251.50	2523.39
Rwanda	1991.74	2179.15	2037.59	1827.36	2025.80
Senegal	2440.90	2194.54	2221.27	2147.85	2255.88
Uganda	2322.98	2268.48	2203.77	2237.99	2279.20

Source: FAOSTAT

This trend has not, however, been equal across the continent. While per capita food

consumption (measured in kilocalories) in SSA has been increasing by an average rate of one % per decade, it has been decreasing in Kenya, Cote D'Ivoire, and DRC by three, one, and nine %s respectively. Conversely, food consumption has been increasing in Ethiopia, Ghana, Nigeria, South Africa, and Tanzania by an average rate of two, seven, nine, two, and three %s per decade, respectively. Further, total food consumption in Benin, Burkina Faso, Burundi, Cameroon, Gambia, Guinea Bissau, Madagascar, Malawi, Mali, Rwanda, Senegal and Uganda has been growing by an average growth rate per decade of 6.75%, 11.52%, -5.52%, 2.18%, -0.93%, 5.99%, -4.54%, -1.33%, 10.49%, 0.42%, -1.95%, and -0.47%, respectively

2.2 Characteristics of Food Security in Africa

Food security in Africa has been a major concern to world leaders and African leaders in particular. Many programs and agendas have been initiated to eliminate hunger in the continent of Africa, mostly in the SSA region, where food insecurity continues to grow. The Millennium Development Goals program set up by the United Nations in the year 2000 was not realized in Africa, and the continuous quest to eliminate hunger in the world brought about the establishment of the Sustainable Development Goal (UN SDGs 2016)

Many factors characterize food insecurity in Africa, drought and conflict are the main factors that have exacerbated the problem of food production, distribution, and access. High rates of population growth and poverty have also played a part in an already difficult environment of fragile ecosystems. The fact that almost 80 % of the population of the countries of the region is rural, and depends almost exclusively on agriculture for its consumption and income needs, means that measures to address the problems of poverty and food insecurity must mainly be found within the agricultural sector.

Poor agricultural productivity, characterized by rain-fed agriculture, limited public investment, and poor access to high-yielding seed varieties and low fertilizer input, leading to chronic food deficit, persistent rural poverty, high food insecurity, and limited availability and unaffordability of nutrient-dense fruits, vegetables, and animal-source foods combined with gender disparities and socio-cultural factors, these challenges adversely affect nutrition for women and children in LMICs.

2.3 Factors of Food Insecurity

Many factors cause food insecurity and hunger, often being intertwined with one another. In general, the principal causes of hunger include poverty, conflict, climate and weather, lack of investment in agriculture, and unstable markets (World Food Programme, 2018)

Table 4: Predominant Motive of Food Insecurity in SSA

Poverty	Poverty is a principal cause of hunger in Africa and elsewhere. Individuals living in poverty often cannot afford food of sufficient quality or quantity to live a healthy life. According to the World Bank, in 2013, 42.3% of the population of sub-Saharan Africa lived on \$1.90 or less per day, a principal factor of widespread hunger. Poverty is often a cycle. Children exposed to long-term undernutrition are often stunted, leading to long-term consequences, including decreased labor productivity and income-earning potential (FAO, 2017).
Conflict	Conflict and violence can, directly and indirectly, impact all levels of the food system, leading to food insecurity and hunger. Conflict often puts constraints on employment and income opportunities, which affects an individual's ability to acquire food. Conflict can also affect exports and imports, which can lead to limited food availability and affordability. Food availability can also be affected if resources (land, equipment, etc.) used to produce food are destroyed during times of conflict (FAO, 2017). In 2017, conflict was the major cause of food insecurity and hunger in 18 countries, affecting about 74 million individuals. Eleven of these countries were in Africa, which totaled about 37 million people. Northern Nigeria, the Democratic Republic of Congo, Somalia, and South Sudan account for the majority of these individuals (Food Security Information Network, 2018). Since 2013, South Sudan has experienced ongoing conflict, which has caused an increase in food insecurity. In 2017, parts of South Sudan declared

	famine, and more than 42% of the population faced severe food insecurity (FAO, 2017).
Governance	<p>As mentioned above, there is a clear connection between conflict and hunger, but poor governance and policies also lead to hunger due to insufficient access to food.</p> <p>Many countries have seen progress in reducing hunger among their citizens after implementing policies that increase food security. For example, in the early 2000s, Ethiopia invested in agricultural research and extension, leading to increases in food availability. This increased investment in infrastructure helped move crops to markets, increasing food access (IFPRI, 2017).</p> <p>Consuming poor-quality food can lead to malnutrition. Policies such as food fortification programs can increase the availability of nutritious foods. The implementation of iodine fortification programs in countries such as Kenya, Rwanda, Tanzania, and Zimbabwe have been successful (Mijumbi, 2011)</p>
Population Growth	Africa's population has increased rapidly, from 221 million in 1950 to 1.2 billion in 2018. Africa has the highest population growth rate among world regions; between 2010 and 2015, it grew at a rate of 2.55% per year. It is estimated that more than half of the global population growth between now and 2050 will occur in Africa (United Nations, 2018). Rapid population growth can limit increases in per capita income, causing poverty and hunger.
Terrorism	Terrorism has been a major factor recently contributing most in food insecurity in SSA countries, Nigeria ,Cameroun ,Chad and Niger has suffered a lot from terror attack , leading to killing from farmers and destroying of farm land and farm produce.

Source: FAO

2.4 Measurement of Food Security

As mentioned earlier, there are five commonly used methods for assessing food security in food security:

- i) the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) method for estimating calories available *per capita* at the national level;
- ii) household income and expenditure surveys;
- iii) individual's dietary intake;
- iv) anthropometry;
- v) experience-based food insecurity measurement scales.

Here, focused will be on the on the Prevalence of undernourishment (%) (3-year average), Prevalence of severe food insecurity in the total population (%) (3-year average) and Dietary energy supply used in the estimation of prevalence of undernourishment (kcal/cap/day) (3-year average). Africa countries mostly from the Western Saharan, were used by FAO due to the existing data in the region. Also due to lack of accurate and reliable data for the different countries:

Prevalence of Undernourishment (%) (10-year average)

Food insecurity is more observed in the selected countries; the Prevalence of Undernourished in 2018 -2020 was obvious due to the pandemic.

Figure 8:: Prevalence of Undernourishment

Source: FAO

Dietary Energy Intake

According to FAO, individual energy intakes in Sub-Saharan African countries show that the region has made a little improvement in dietary energy intake from 2009-2018, but the year after the emergence of the Covid-19 led to the decrease in the daily calorie intake due to many factors. (Figure10)

Figure 9: Dietary Energy Intake

Source: FAO

Prevalence of Severe Food Insecurity In The Total Population % (10yr Av)

According to the data available from 2014-2020 in six Sub-Saharan countries, there was a steady increase in the prevalence of severe food insecurity in the total population of five countries (Burkina Faso, Gambia, Ghana, Malawi, and Sierra Leone), Nigeria was the only country that recorded a little decrease in a number of the severe food insecure in the total population.

Figure 10:Prevalence of Severe Food Insecurity in the Total Population % (10yr Av)

Source: FAOSTAT

In the number of severely food insecure people in the six Sub-Saharan countries, there was a steady increase in the numbers each country recorded an increase, and Nigeria recorded the highest number of the total population.

Figure 11:Number of severely food insecure people in Million (10yr Av) 2014-2020

Suite of food security indicators

Source: FAO

The number of people undernourished in Sub-Sahara Africa has continue to rise even as some of the countries recorded a slight decrease in some years, many of the countries still have a larger number who are people undernourished in the region.

Figure 12: Number of people Undernourished (Million) (10yrs Av) 2011-2020

Source: FAO

Level of Food Insecurity in Sub-Saharan Africa

Almost one in four people in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) were estimated to be undernourished in 2017, representing about one-third of the 821 million people suffering from chronic hunger globally (FAO et al., 2018). In addition to a high prevalence of chronic hunger in SSA, many more people suffer from micronutrient deficiencies (Joy et al., 2014; Kumssa et al., 2015; Harika et al., 2017)

In the 2017 and 2018 editions of the Africa Regional Overview of Food Security and Nutrition, FAO reported that the prevalence of undernourishment was rising in the region. The latest data shows that the deterioration has slowed, but there remain 256 million hungry people in Africa today, with 17 million in Northern Africa and 239 million in sub-Saharan Africa. This report, which builds on the past two editions, shows that the worsening food insecurity situation is due to climate shocks, conflict, and economic slowdowns and downturns, sometimes overlapping. These factors continue to be the main causes of food insecurity in the region.

The rise in the prevalence of undernourishment in sub-Saharan Africa over the 2014 to 2018 period was widespread and provides a detailed, country-focused discussion of the underlying factors (identifying conflict, climate extremes, and economic slowdowns and downturns as the main drivers) of rising food insecurity during that period. The 2017 edition of this report detailed how conflicts in the region primarily affected rural areas, damaging activities across the food

system (which encompasses the entire range of actors and their interlinked activities involved in the production, aggregation, processing, distribution, consumption, and disposal of food products). The resulting disruption or destruction of livelihood constitutes a major cause of acute and chronic food insecurity and various forms of malnutrition. The 2018 edition focused on climate variability and extremes as key drivers of the recent rise in food insecurity and two of the leading causes of the severe food crises that have affected the continent. They, directly and indirectly, undermine food availability, access, utilization, and stability with grave consequences for immediate and long-term food security and nutrition outcomes, especially for children.

Prevalence of Moderate or Severe Food Insecurity in Sub-Saharan Africa

In 2017, FAO introduced the prevalence of severe food insecurity based on the Food Insecurity Experience Scale (FIES) as a complementary indicator of hunger to FAO's traditional indicator, the PoU, to provide additional information on the access dimension of food security. At the time, the prevalence of severe food insecurity based on the Food Insecurity Experience Scale (FIES) was reported at the regional and sub-regional level. 2017 marks the first time that the prevalence of moderate and severe food insecurity has been reported in countries that have authorized FAO to publish the estimates. The Food Insecurity Experience Scale (FIES) is based on data collected directly from representative samples of individuals. As measured by this indicator, food insecurity refers to limited access to food, at the level of individuals or households, due to a lack of money or other resources. The resulting FIES indicator is an estimate of the proportion of the population who face moderate or severe constraints on their ability to obtain sufficient food for a year.

Figure 13: Food Security Level

Source: FAO

The measure of moderate or severe food insecurity also shows that in addition to the 277 million people in Africa who are severely food insecure, there are 399 million people who are moderately food insecure, i.e., they did not have regular access to nutritious and sufficient food, even if they were not necessarily suffering from hunger. Of these, 87 % live in Sub-Saharan Africa.

Table 5: Prevalence of moderate or severe food insecurity (measured using fies) in the world, Africa and its subregions, 2014 - 2018 (%)

Prevalence of severe food insecurity in the total population (%)					Prevalence of moderate or severe food insecurity in the total population (%)					
Regions/subregions	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
Africa	18.1	19.0	21.9	22.9	21.5	47.6	48.3	52.6	54.3	52.5
Northern Africa	8.6	7.2	9.3	10.1	8.0	27.1	22.9	27.8	35.2	29.5
Sub-Saharan Africa	20.3	21.7	24.8	25.8	24.6	54.2	58.3	58.7	57.7	52.4
Central Africa	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a
Eastern Africa	23.9	25.1	27.8	28.7	25.9	58.2	59.7	64.8	65.5	62.7
Southern Africa	21.4	20.6	30.7	30.8	30.6	45.3	45.9	53.5	53.6	53.6
Western Africa	12.9	14.4	16.5	17.7	17.6	43.7	45.3	47.3	47.7	47.9

Source: FAO uses the M49 country and regional groupings, available at <https://unstats.un.org/unsd/methodology/m49>. In this report, “Central Africa” refers to the M49 “Middle Africa” grouping.

2.6 Forms of Coping With Food Insecurity

The COVID-19 pandemic has had significant negative impacts on people's incomes and livelihoods across the world. According to the World Bank, global GDP per capita was expected to decline by 6.2% in 2020, while Sub-Saharan Africa and South Asia were expected to suffer 5.3% and 3% declines, respectively. This loss of income, combined with the associated use of lockdowns to control the spread of the virus, has had severe repercussions on access to food, and food insecurity more broadly, particularly in lower-income countries

Several different coping mechanisms were used in response to the stress of household food insecurity. In SSA, the coping mechanisms identified were: decreasing frequency and portions of meals, borrowing food and money, receiving food and monetary aid, selling permanent assets, harvesting faster crops, migrating for work, engaging in labor jobs, becoming involved in small businesses, creating hand-made crafts, begging, and selling wood and charcoal. The most common coping mechanism employed by households in the study was to decrease the usual meal frequency and the amount of food. This strategy was used by 55.96% of households out of the total households affected by food insecurity in Sub-Sahara Africa

Coping Strategies

Selling assets and reducing food consumption: The World Bank provides more disaggregated data on coping mechanisms. Here, we focus on two particularly severe coping mechanisms with potentially adverse long-term consequences for household wellbeing (i) the sale of agricultural or non-agricultural assets and (ii) the reduction of food consumption. Figure 5 shows the share of households (of those who experienced a reduction of income) that sold agricultural or non-agricultural assets. Between 1% and 17% of households reported to have sold assets. We observe diverging trends in Ethiopia and Nigeria. Ethiopia experienced a decrease from 4% which reported asset sales in April to only 1% in May. In Nigeria, however, the share that sold assets increased from 5% in May to 12% in July. This is a worrying development. Uganda reports 2% who sold assets in June. The share of households reporting a reduction in food consumption. Between 13% and 69% of households that experienced a reduction in income reduced their food consumption. In Nigeria, reduction in food intake is particularly widespread, and an increasing 54% reported food reduction in May and 69% in July. In Ethiopia, 13% reported reduced food consumption in

April and 20% in May, also a significant increase. In Uganda, 16% reported reduced food consumption in June.

Figure 14: Household (%) Selling Assets Consumption

Figure 15: Households (%) Reducing Food Consumption

Households Selling Assets

Source: LSMS-Supported High-Frequency Phone Surveys on COVID-19

Social Assistance

The previous section showed that the use of informal coping strategies is high overall. Societal welfare would be improved by replacing these inefficient informal insurance mechanisms with social insurance, e.g., income/cash transfers. States and communities have mobilized social assistance and resources to help those who are most heavily affected. Figure 6 shows that in the four countries where there is data available, the share of the population that has received any type of assistance ranges between 6% and 16%. This is a low share compared to those who ran out of food or were unable to buy staple food.

Note that for most countries, the WB does not provide data on the share of the population that received assistance but the share of the population that received specific types of social assistance,

such as food aid, cash transfers, or non-food transfers. Since, in principle, one household can receive several forms of assistance, it is impossible to calculate the aggregate based on these figures. In the Figure below, it can be assumed for simplicity that there is no such overlap, and the figure thus shows the maximum share of the population that may have received assistance. The exception is Ethiopia, where the data represent the actual share of the population that received any form of assistance.

Figure 16:Households that Received Assistance

Source: LSMS-Supported High-Frequency Phone Surveys on COVID-19

CHAPTER 3 CHARACTERISTICS OF FOOD CONSUMPTION

A theoretical model of modern food consumption is presented built on the assumption that utility from different food characteristics is accumulated over time. The characteristics considered include energy content, taste, health, status, environmental (as well as political and ethical) proprieties, time, and financial cost. Another assumption is that food is usually consumed as meals, that is, as bundles of different characteristics. The better the combination of foods chosen over a period (i.e., a diet comprising meals that offer many utility-increasing characteristics relative to the most restrictive utility-decreasing one), the higher the overall utility will be at the end of the period.

In sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), rural communities traditionally prepare meals from locally grown crops like cassava, sorghum, and pulses. However, with rapid population growth, massive urbanization, and increasing disposable incomes, consumption of refined wheat bread is rapidly increasing and displacing traditional meals. Major economic and food and nutrition security problems are resulting from this transition. The double nutritional burden is prevalent throughout SSA, with urban and peri-urban regions being most vulnerable, and is certain to increase as the nutrition transition advances. Africa now imports nearly 60% of its wheat, with, for example, Nigeria and Ghana importing some 71% and 69%, respectively, of their domestic needs. There are opportunities for Africa to reduce its dependency on wheat imports by replacing wheat flour with flour made from locally grown crops. This change is needed to improve food security, provide markets and regular income to smallholder farmers and create new business opportunities along the crop value chain (Guiné, 2022). Furthermore, the transition of SSA agriculture to producing crops that are more resilient to abiotic stresses like drought, heat, and flooding is crucial in the face of the climate change predicted for shorter- and longer-term future

Food consumption goes beyond eating three square meals per day but eating the right balanced diet and also the nutrient content of the food. Many households in Sub-Saharan Africa may eat more than two square meals per day but lack the minimum necessary balanced diet required for healthy living, as suggested by the FAO. The key driver for eating is hunger, but what we choose to eat is not determined solely by physiological or nutritional needs. Some of the other factors that influence food choice include:

- Biological determinants such as hunger, appetite, and taste

- Economic determinants such as cost, income, availability
- Physical determinants such as access, education, skills (e.g., cooking) and time
- Social determinants such as culture, family, peers and meal patterns
- Psychological determinants such as mood, stress and guilt
- Attitudes, beliefs and knowledge about food

3.1 Dietary Food Consumption in Africa

The need to shift to more sustainable diets and food systems is increasingly evident but certainly not simple to achieve, especially in the Sahel region. According to FAO approach, the sustainability of diets goes beyond nutrition and environment as to include economic and socio-cultural dimensions.

More countries have started incorporating sustainability considerations into their food policies and consumer education programmes. Given the policy and programmatic implications of Food Based Dietary Guidelines (FBDGs), developing and integrating recommendations that promote specific food practices and choices have been an obvious strategy for addressing sustainability, mainly in its nutrition and environment dimensions.

Income, prices, individual preferences and beliefs, cultural traditions, as well as geographical, environmental, social and economic factors all interact in a complex manner to shape dietary consumption patterns. In low-income countries, 11 % of dietary energy is derived from roots and tubers, 6 % from grain legumes, 3 % from animal products and the remainder is made up mainly of cereals (Schönfeldt & Hall, 2012). African diets are usually based on one or several carbohydrate-rich staples, generally eaten in the form of a stiff ‘porridge’, served with soups, relishes and sauces prepared from a wide variety of other foodstuffs (FAO, 1997). In most African countries, staple cereals such as maize, sorghum, millet, and rice contribute 40% to 60 % of the total dietary energy supply and, therefore, a considerable contribution to the protein intake. Maize is one of Africa’s dominant food crops consumed throughout Africa as a staple food (International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA), 2009). The relish provides oil, protein, vitamins and minerals, making the starchy staple more palatable. The components and the nature of the starchy staple will remain fairly constant within a community. At the same time, the relish (usually

composed of vegetables, grain legumes and fish or meat if available) will vary in components, flavor and consistency depending on the season, household resources, and dietary habits (FAO, 1997). The diets in different African regions, an example of staple food and a sauce recipe, the macronutrients and micronutrients within the African diet, and the consumption of grain legumes in Africa are discussed

In the drier areas in the north of West Africa, the staple foods are sorghum or millet, which have a fairly good protein value. The rainy season is short, so there is usually a shortage of food before the next harvest. Maize, cassava, and sweet potatoes are also common. In the savannah country of East Africa, maize has largely replaced millet and sorghum as staple foods. Meat and milk consumption is higher than in West Africa because the raising of cattle plays a more prominent role in local agricultural practices. Severe droughts are the chief hazard to food supplies in the area. Plantains, starchy roots, and tubers are the main staples in the tropical rainforest areas of West and Central Africa. The disease associated with protein deficiency is the most common here. One crop is usually dominant, for example, cassava in much of the DRC, plantains in parts of Uganda and Ghana, and yams in Nigeria. Meat is rare; the only source of animal protein is small game such as chicken, guinea fowls, rabbits, guinea pigs, and bush meat. There are normally no seasonal food shortages in the rainforest areas and no disastrous droughts, but occasional tornadoes cause damage. The soil is sometimes too poor to raise sufficient food. Outside of the temperate zones, in the southern part of the continent, a greater variety of fruits and vegetables are available, including bananas, pineapples, papaya, mangoes, avocados, tomatoes, and carrots, onions, potatoes, and cabbage.

Nonetheless, the traditional meal in southern Africa is also centered on a staple crop; usually, rice or maize, served with a stew. The most common dish made from maize flour is called mealie meal or pap, sadza, and nshima or nsima. The stew may include a few boiled vegetables, such as cabbage or spinach, or fish, beans, or chicken on more special occasions. Like other regions of Africa, much of the diets in the countries of North Africa (extending from Morocco to Iran) are based on cereals. However, cooking with olive oil, onions, and garlic is more common, and as the countries are largely Muslim, no pork is consumed, and alcohol is forbidden (Stanton, 1966). Milk is scarcely consumed throughout Africa (except in some countries such as Kenya, Mauritania, and Somalia) because of the very low production of milk per animal and the lack of preservation technology (FAO, 1997). In addition to these broad groups, there are some tribes whose diet was originally

almost entirely based on livestock products but they now barter some of these for cereals. There are also groups living near lakes, rivers or the seas who eat fairly large quantities of fish. The West, East and South African diets are described in more detail in Appendix V. In West Africa cowpeas are mixed with rice, maize or sorghum and with gari (dried fermented cassava flour) or plantain. In these mixes, grain legumes provide a supplementary value to protein requirements (quantity and/or quality), to mineral and vitamin requirements and they also contribute towards variety in taste and texture. Further, grain legumes, particularly groundnuts and chickpeas, are popular as snack foods and contribute towards energy intake. Fried bean-flour cakes are commonly eaten in West Africa. Figure below shows the consumption of different diets in selected Sub-Saharan Africa regions.

Table 6: Average intake (g/person/day) 2021

	Cereals	Fish Seafood	Fruit	Meat	Milk	Oil crops	Pulses	Starchy Roots	Sugars, Sweetener	Vegetable Oil	Vegetable
Burkina Faso	605	6	14	31	56	42	14	16	15	13	47
Burundi	84	5	284	10	13	2	103	632	8	2	93
Cameroon	288	38	213	41	40	19	39	400	28	21	217
Congo, Dem. Rep of	102	16	82	13	4	12	10	842	8	15	25
Cote d'Ivoire	331	40	201	31	21	20	1	619	30	37	103
Ethiopia	384	1	28	23	61	2	35	168	12	4	31
Ghana	249	80	319	27	21	35	2	1107	19	16	88
Kenya	337	12	154	40	263	4	42	164	55	20	102
Malawi	403	10	107	14	12	13	34	504	31	9	54
Mali	502	21	8	51	126	5	25	30	30	18	66
Mozambique	289	6	48	15	12	5	26	665	31	19	17

Nigeria	399	20	185	23	20	21	26	593	31	38	167
Sudan	370	5	83	59	410	11	22	13	55	21	135
Uganda	170	20	556	31	67	35	65	561	24	5	55
United Rep. of Tanzania	307	19	81	27	70	14	28	518	21	14	76
Zimbabwe	355	4	32	42	54	17	13	43	97	26	30

Source: Kokwaro.

There are over a hundred kinds of food in Africa dating back, but the two common ones are cereals and legumes, which are the main sources of diets in the SSA:

The value of the contribution of legumes to good nutrition can be assessed by studying them in the context of human eating patterns. Humankind has survived because they have been able to locate and later cultivate sufficient nutritious food to fulfill their requirements. The instinct for eating mixtures of a wide selection of foods is deep-rooted and is still evident. Legumes play an important part in this diversity. Diets based on starchy staples tend to be monotonous and unappetizing. Therefore, they are eaten with sauces and relishes made from a variety of foods, including grain legumes. This not only gives an appetizing taste and texture but also adds nutrients to the staple dish, ensuring a balanced diet, and meeting nutrient requirements (Aykroyd & Doughty, 1982). Grain legumes are part of two important complementary mixes: cereals and grain legumes and starchy roots and fruits and grain legumes. The additive nutritional value of grain legumes within the African diet is discussed in the contribution to protein, energy, and micronutrient requirements. The literature is reviewed to find evidence on the efficacy of the consumption of legume-based foods on nutritional intake and the status of the most vulnerable groups for nutrient deficiencies: reproductive women, children, and infants.

Within West Africa, there is considerable variation in staple food. Rice is predominant from Mauritania to Liberia and across to the Sahel, a region that stretches across the continent between the Sahara and the southern savannahs. Couscous is the prevalent dish in the Sahara. Along the coast from Cote d'Ivoire (Ivory Coast) to Nigeria and Cameroon, root crops, primarily varieties of yam and cassava, are common. Cassava, imported from Brazil by the Portuguese, is boiled and

then pounded into a nearly pure starch. Yam is the chief crop in West Africa and is served in a variety of dishes, including Amala (pounded yam). Millet is also used for making porridge or beer. Palm oil is the base of stew in the Gambia, southern, and eastern regions. In the Saharan area, groundnut paste (peanut butter) is the main ingredient for stew. Other stews are based on okra (a vegetable native to the rainforests of Africa), beans, sweet potato leaves, or cassava. Other vegetables are eggplant, cabbage, carrots, chilies, French beans, lettuce, onions, and cherry tomatoes. All the stews in this territory tend to be heavily spiced, often with chilies. Meat sources of protein include cattle, sheep, chicken, and goat, though beef is normally reserved for special occasions. Fish is eaten in the coastal areas. Because of the Islamic influence, pork is localized to non-Muslim areas. In these regions, “bush meat” is widely eaten, including bush rats, a large herbivorous rodent, antelope, and monkeys. Giant snails are also eaten in various parts of West Africa.

Extensive trade and migrations with Arabic countries and South Asia have made East African culture unique, particularly on the coast. The main staples include potatoes, rice, mataka (mashed plantains), and a maize meal that is cooked up into a thick porridge. Beans or a stew with meat, potatoes, or vegetables often accompany the porridge. Beef, goat, chicken, or sheep are the most common meats. Outside of Kenya and the horn of Africa, the stew is not as spicy, but the coastal area has spicy, coconut-based stews. This is quite unique compared to the central and southern parts of Africa. Two herding tribes, the Maasai and Fulbe, have different eating patterns. They do not eat very much meat, except for special occasions. Instead, they subsist on fresh and soured milk and butter as their staples. This is unusual because very few Africans consume milk or dairy products due to lactose intolerance. The horn of Africa, which includes modern-day Somalia and Ethiopia, is characterized by its remarkably spicy food prepared with chilies and garlic. The staple grain, teff, has a considerably higher iron and nutrient content than other grain staples found in Africa. A common traditional food here is injera, a spongy flat bread that is eaten by tearing it, then using it to scoop up the meat or stew.

Outside of the temperate zones, a greater variety of fruits and vegetables are available in the southern part of the continent. Fruits and vegetables in southern Africa include bananas, pineapples, papaya, mangoes, avocados, tomatoes, carrots, onions, potatoes, and cabbage. Nonetheless, the traditional meal in southern Africa is centered on a staple crop, usually, rice or maize served with a stew. The most common dish made from maize flour is called mealie meal,

or pap in South Africa. Also known as nshima or nsima further north, it is usually eaten with stew. The stew may include a few boiled vegetables, such as cabbage, spinach, or turnips, or fish, beans, or chicken on more special occasions.

3.2 Comparing Different Indicators of Food Security Used In Africa and Developed Countries

There are several indicators to be considered in the context of food security. The Global Food Security Index (GFSI) considers the issue of food affordability, availability, quality and safety, and natural resilience to be the based for food security.

African countries are poorly developed, which primarily does not guarantee food affordability, availability, quality and safety, and natural resilience. A developed country is one that boasts features such as a developed economy, a stable and functional government, a robust infrastructure, a strong educational system, ample job opportunities, comprehensive health and social services, and a high degree of personal freedom. Countries that fall slightly short of these goals are classified as developing countries. Those that fall far short are designated the least developed countries and become eligible for specific United Nations assistance programs. The most widely used and respected measure of a country's development status is the United Nations' annual Human Development Index (HDI). This advanced metric tracks a wide range of indicators, from Adult Literacy Rate and Life Expectancy to Income Inequality and Mobile Phone Subscription, then compile them all into a number between 0.00 and 1.00. This score slots each country into one of four different classifications: low human development (0-.55), medium human development (.55-.70), high human development (.70-80), and very high human development (.80-1.0).

Most developed countries have a score of at least .80 and are considered "very high human development." That said, Africa is the least-developed continent outside of Antarctica, with many of its countries still mired in issues including poverty, government corruption, and armed conflict. As of the 2020 HDI, only one of Africa's 54 countries is considered to have "very high human development." On the bright side, some African countries have "high human development", and could reach the Very High plateau soon. (See chapter three)

As mentioned earlier the FAO considers the four pillars of food security (Availability, Access, Utilization and Stability) as the simple indicators that determine the level of food security and well-being of the people. Developing countries mostly in SSA regions are exposed to a high risk of malnutrition related diseases due to food insecurity and poverty. In chapter two it discussed the factors of food insecurity (Poverty, Conflict, Education, Climate and Weather, lack of investment in agriculture, etc.) which has kept one in five - 21% of the Africa population in severe hunger and 282 million people undernourished in 2020.

. In the table below, the four pillars of food security were used as an indicator to compare the SSA and the developed countries level of food security

Table 7: Food Security Score for SSA and Developed Countries

Indicators		Africa/ Sub-Saharan	Developed Countries
Food Availability		35%	75%
Food Access		30%	70%
Food Utilization		35%	70%
Food Stability		30%	75%

Source: FAOSTAT

There are five commonly used methods that can be used to assess food security: i) the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) method for estimating calories available *per capita* at the national level; ii) household income and expenditure surveys; iii) individual's dietary intake; iv) Here, three of the methods that are always used in determining the level food security will be considered, using a simple variable to compare the level of food security in developing countries to developed.

FAO Method

This method estimates calories *per capita* at the country level using Food Balance Sheets and energy intake variance data derived from household income and expenditure surveys. Countries need the following information to be able to apply this method:

- i) Total calories available in year of interest;
- ii) Number of people living in country in year of interest;

- iii) Coefficient of variation of caloric intake to generate the energy intake distribution curve;
- iv) Cut-off point to estimate the proportion of the population falling under the minimum *per capita* average caloric requirement.

Table 7, is a comparison between country A (Developed) and country B (Developing). The total number of household members in family A is just a couple and a child, and the monthly income was assumed to be (\$4500) from both the employed husband and the wife. The daily calorie intake is equal to 3600kcal per family member, and the monthly total cost of living, including rent, is \$2000. Also, enjoy different food choices with a satisfactory standard of living (75%). The monthly saves in household A = \$2500, which can be used for luxury and to take good care of their only child.

A

B

Table 8: Comparing Developed to SSA

Total Numbers of family size	3 Persons	Total Number of Family Size	6 Persons
Family income	\$4500	Family income	\$1500
Daily Calories	3600Kcal p/p	Daily Calories	2450kcal p/p
Monthly expenditure	\$2000	Monthly expenditure	\$1250
No of h/h member employed	2	No of h/h member employed	1
Food choice	Yes	Food choice	No
Standard of living	High (75%)	Standard of living	Low (40%)
Rent	\$500	Rent	\$250

Source: Data4diets.

In the case of country B, the total number of household members is the couple and four children and the man (husband) being the only employed person with a monthly income of \$1500. The daily calorie intake in the family is equal to 2450kcal per family member, and the monthly total cost of living, including rent in a small apartment, is \$1250. Country B household having four children and an unemployed wife with a monthly leftover of \$250, would not be able to provide a

balanced diet for the household, and the children might be denied quality education, and the entire household would live below the standard of living (table)

Table 9: Household Food Security Indicators for Both Households

Food Security Indicators	A	B
Depth of food deficit	30%	70%
Food consumption score (FCS)	75%	35%
Household food insecurity scale (HFIS)	30%	70%
Household hunger scale (HHS)	25%	65%
Household adequacy of fruit and vegetable consumption	65%	15%
Household food expenditure share	60%	40%
Household average dietary food acquisition and consumption	65%	35%

Source: Data4diets.

3.3. Income and Expenditure

The share of total household expenditure (as a proxy of income) spent on food is an indicator of household food security because it is widely documented that the poorer and more vulnerable a household, the larger the share of household income spent on food. Using Engel's law, which proves that as incomes rise, both within a country and across countries, expenditure on food increases while expenditure on other things increases even more so that the share of total income

spent on food declines. Given this observation, the indicator is especially helpful in understanding the impact of food price fluctuations on both the quality and quantity of household food consumption.

If a change in food prices results in a higher share of total household expenditure is spent on food, then this can result in the household being more resource constrained (i.e., poorer) as a result of the increase in food prices. Consequently, depending on the specific foods, households that are very poor and already consuming the lowest-cost foods will be unable to substitute cheaper foods and will be forced to spend more on basic staples, reduce the quality of their diets, or even reduce the quantity consumed of the least expensive foods, while also reducing non-food expenditures that may be equally needed (e.g., on health and education) (Lele et al., 2016)

This indicator is commonly calculated with data from Household Consumption and Expenditure Surveys (HCES) that include the monetary value of household consumption disaggregated into food and non-food items. The share of household expenditure on food is equal to:

$$I = \frac{\textit{Expenditure on food}}{\textit{Total expenditure}} \times 100$$

Total expenditure

The monetary value of non-purchased items, including consumption from own production and in-kind payments and transfers, must be imputed from available price information.

While no internationally agreed thresholds exist, Smith and Subandoro (2007) Have proposed that households spending over 75% of their income on food are considered very vulnerable and consequently food insecure, whereas people spending 65-75% are considered to have high food insecurity; those spending 50-65% have medium food insecurity; and those that spend less than 50% of their income on food are considered to have lower levels of food insecurity.

This indicator is one of several indicators included in the ADePT-FSM (Food Security Module) software package, a free standalone software developed by the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) and the World Bank that allows users to derive food security indicators from household survey data easily. The software download and corresponding documentation can be found on the FAO website.

Household Consumption and Expenditure Surveys (HCES)—also referred to by a variety of other names including Household Income and Expenditure Surveys (HIES), Household Budget Surveys (HBS), or Living Standards Measurement Surveys (LSMS)—are complex surveys conducted on a nationally representative sample to characterize important aspects of household socioeconomic

conditions (Coates et al., 2012). Typically, HCES are conducted every 3-5 years in a range of countries and cover 7,000 to 20,000 households to provide a statistically representative sample (Fiedler et al., 2012). Most HCES are implemented by national statistical agencies, often with technical assistance from the World Bank's Living Standard Measurement Study (LSMS) group. The results of HCES have wide-ranging utility. Their primary purpose is to provide information for poverty monitoring, the calculation of national accounts, and as an input for consumer price indices (Smith et al., 2014). However, there is increasing interest in using the food consumption module from HCES as a source of nationally representative data for assessing food security and nutrition. Furthermore, HCES collects a wide range of data on determinants and outcomes (e.g., socioeconomic status, education), potentially enriching food security and nutrition analyses. Based on existing research there is wide consensus that HCES, with carefully designed consumption modules, are a valuable source of data for household-level food security and nutrition measurement (Russell et al., 2018; Zezza et al., 2017).

One of the major drawbacks of using HCES is that the consumption modules are heterogeneous across countries, which means that not all HCES data lend themselves to the same food security and nutrition analyses, and comparisons across countries can be inaccurate. Some of the key ways in which the consumption modules differ across surveys include: 1) the length of the recall period; 2) whether data are collected for acquisition, consumption, or both; 3) whether there is information on the mode of food acquisition (purchases, own production, and in-kind); 4) whether or not information on food consumed away from home is collected and in what form; 5) whether food detail is collected through open recall or a list, and, if a list, how disaggregated and specific the foods and food groups are; and 6) the use of non-standard units without available conversions (Smith et al., 2014). For example, if the food consumption module has a short food list with aggregated items making it difficult to match with a food composition database, excludes food away from home, and has a long recall period (>14 days), then the consumption module may not be adequate for measuring certain food security and nutrition indicators, such as total household-level calorie availability.

While the 'C' in HCES stands for 'consumption', HCES collects data on acquisition, consumption, or both. While consumption data refers to the food consumed by the household, acquisition data refers to the food acquired through purchases, own production, and in-kind. Acquisition data serves as a proxy for food consumption, as households may build food stocks or consume food

stocks during the reference period, as compared to consumption, which collects data on food consumed in a specified period. This is an important point because some foods (e.g., grains) are not perishable and can be stored therefore some households may be drawing down stocks acquired to meet current consumption, while other households may be accumulating stocks that will be consumed after that period (Smith et al., 2014). Another type of HCES collects a combination of acquisition and consumption data; wherein households report what they acquired through purchases and what they consumed from their own-production and transfers (Smith, 2003). Food consumption estimates generated from acquisition data or a combination of both acquisition and consumption data are typically referred to as 'apparent consumption in the literature to distinguish it from actual consumption (Fiedler & Mwangi, 2016).

The World Bank Microdata Library has the most comprehensive and publicly accessible repository of HCES data. Data also can be accessed from countries' National Statistics Office, though each country has its own policies and procedures regarding data sharing. The International Household Survey Network (IHSN) is an informal network to promote data standards and dissemination where additional information (e.g., survey catalogs, guidelines, and software) on existing HCES can be found (IHSN, 2018).

3.4. Socio-economic Status as an Indicator of Food Insecurity

Socio-economic status (SES) usually refers to components of economic and social status that distinguish and characterize people (Morris et al. 2000). While the relationship between SES and health has received increasing notice over the past 5 decades, relatively little attention has been given to defining SES, validating existing definitions or evaluating existing measures. Lack of conceptual clarity and bypassing standard techniques have retarded the measurement of SES (Oakes and Rossi 2003). Indicators of SES are meant to reflect access to social and economic resources that may vary over time (Duncan et al. 2002). Many indicators of SES exist (see Oakes and Rossi 2003 for complete description); however, there is little agreement over which indicators are most useful (Winkleby et al. 1992). In the context of developing countries, even greater challenges exist in measuring SES, because many indicators are unreliable and insensitive in the framework of developing world economies.

Frequent measures of SES in developing countries (Saharan Africa) include proxies of wealth, income, expenditures, education and housing conditions (Morris et al. 2000). Recent research in Africa alone uses a multitude of indicators, suggesting there is little consensus within the research community. In addition to controlling for educational attainment and housing conditions, studies used self-reported income, asset ownership, expenditures, and indices built on a combination of these factors or principal components analysis (Kannae and Pendelton 1998; Groenwald and Tilahun 1990; Manunebo et al. 1994; Kuate Defo 1994; Morris et al. 2000; Carme et al. 1994; Mock et al. 1993; Gage 1997; Omar et al. 1994; Schellenberg et al. 2003). While measures of SES are consistently associated with health outcomes, indicators are not interchangeable because they measure different components of SES (Adler et al. 1994; Krieger et al. 1997; Williams and Collins 1995; Winkleby et al. 1992). Most field research employs indicators that measure only one or two components of SES; consequently, certain elements of SES are not represented and the degree and significance of correlations between SES measures and health outcomes varies by the components of SES that are assessed.

In many contexts, particularly program evaluations and field research, where the assessment of SES is not the primary objective, SES is measured by a proxy of one of its components (i.e., income, wealth, education, etc.). Studies assess multiple components of SES unless at least one indicator is used as a control variable. Consequently, SES is estimated based on a variety of proxies, which may not have relationships with each other, calling into question the validity and comparability of commonly used indicators. While it is clear that indicators measuring different components of SES are not equivalent, researchers are faced with the challenge of selecting measures of SES that are most relevant to the outcomes of the study, and they face limitations in terms of the reliability and practicality of potential indicators.

All proxies are imperfect measures of SES. The principal drawback of income indicators is they are usually self-reported. Inaccuracies are related to reporting biases from (1) motives to report increased or decreased incomes due to misconceptions (such as the belief that survey responses will qualify respondents for aid; (2) the seasonal nature of incomes in agricultural economies results in an increased likelihood of measurement error when monthly income is reported; (3) rapid inflation may increase the difficulty of estimating income over extended periods of time and result in recall bias; (4) in traditional societies where barter is common, the concept of an annual income

is unfamiliar to individuals who live day-to-day and may not be able to accurately approximate annual income.

Wealth is a component of SES that is often estimated using material assets. Incorporating home and land ownership in wealth measures is important because they are important in agricultural economies. However, estimating land value in the Sub-Saharan regions is difficult because of varying land quality and other factors. Most homes are constructed with a combination of purchased and gathered goods using household labor, making it difficult to attach a monetary value to the home. Valid figures of wealth that include home and land ownership may be difficult to construct in many contexts; alternatively, housing conditions may serve as a useful substitute for wealth, because in most cultures, there is a relationship between wealth and the quality of housing.

Universal problems affecting estimation of SES are the issues of inclusion and weighting of components in the development of indices and composite variables. Weighting of indices and scores could be viewed as arbitrary, as their relative importance is difficult to ascertain, particularly when it may vary by the outcome of the study. Methods such as asset-based approaches depend on the selection of items included in the measure; however, there is no clear and universally accepted methodology for selecting items, nor are there definitive guidelines for using a wider set of assets. Ultimately, issues of component inclusion and weighting are a basis for arguments questioning the validity of composite indicators and indices that are frequently used as a substitute for SES.

Finally, it should be noted that measures of income, wealth and housing conditions in Sub-Saharan Africa ignore intangible non-material assets of social and human capital, both of which are important components of social well-being and SES (Morris et al. 2000). Educational attainment is a common measure of human assets; however, it often fails to directly measure skills associated with income generation. In developing countries where unemployment and underemployment are prevalent, educational attainment may be a poor measure of SES because of the lack of employment opportunities. Similarly, the occupational class may inadequately measure SES, particularly in rural areas where the reported occupational class is likely to be homogeneous. The present study was conducted in Northern Nigeria and Cameroun after a drought that resulted in the inflation of staple food prices and regional food insecurity. As part of a study of coping strategies in the context of chronic drought and food security, we attempted to measure SES using

a variety of indicators. Ideally, an objective measure of well-being could be used to define SES, and commonly-used proxies of SES could be compared to this reference; however, no gold standard indicator exists. In addition to comparing associations between different components of SES, the study examined mid-upper arm circumference (MUAC), an objective measure of physical well-being that is recommended for assessing acute adult malnutrition (FANTA 2003). Nutritional status is a plausible biological measure of physical status in the context of food insecurity because people with better SES are likely to have enhanced nutritional status because they have more resources to meet nutritional needs. In the Sub-Saharan regions, where food insecurity is prevalent, variation in MUAC by SES is anticipated because access to food is most limited in poorer segments of the population.

CHAPTER 4. METHODOLOGY AND THE FINDINGS

4.1 The background of the study

The research conducted is based on the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) and the Global Food Security Index (GFSI), developed by the Economist Intelligence Unit (EIU) in 2012. This composite indicator aims to monitor food security progress at a country (s) level. This synthetic index is a result of 28 indicators grouped in 3 domains (adequate to three dimensions of food security: affordability (6 indicators), availability (11 indicators), and quality and safety (11 indicators) (GFSI annual reports 2019). GFSI focuses on contributing factors to food security rather than on outcomes such as food consumption or the nutritional status of the population. Due to the method of data aggregation, the index, on the one hand, allows a macroeconomic approach to food security, which avoids diversifying the level of food security within a selected country between households (impact economic review 2019). On the other hand, standard data allows for international comparisons in a static and dynamic approach, eliminating the subjectivism of assessments. The analysis is based on GFSI data for 28 countries in Sub-Saharan Africa from 2012–2017. Such a scope of work is determined by the availability of data.

Global Hunger Index (GHI) and Global Food Security Index (GFSI) still put Sub-Saharan Africa behind and have the lowest level of food security. Although in 2017 and 2012, there was an improvement in food security in Sub-Saharan Africa, the relatively high rate of change was mainly the effect of the base as well as the relatively good economic situation in most African countries in 2012–2017. However, the drop in the index in 2017 may be disturbing compared to the previous year. This unfavorable reversal of the trend is also confirmed by research conducted by other measures (FAO, 2015; FAO, 2017).

According to the Global Food Security Index, Sub-Sahara Africa still remains the poorest and has the lowest level of food security. Although there was an improvement in the previous year, 2012 and 2017, in the food security of the Sahel region, the relatively high rate of change was mainly the base's effect and the relatively good economic situation in most African countries in 2012–2017. However, the drop in the index in 2017 may be disturbing compared to the previous year. This unfavorable trend reversal is also confirmed by research conducted by other measures (FAO, 2015; FAO, 2017).

According to the Global Food Security Index (GFSI) current ranking in September 2021, African countries stood at the bottom of the list. Based on the projection, food insecurity in the Sub-Sahara region will double if there is no proper Agricultural mechanism to caution against the continuous rise.

Table 10: SSA Countries Performance Based on their Food Security Score 2021

Global Ranking- SSA	Country	Overall score	Affordability	Availability	Quality and Safety	Natural Resources
70 th (1)	South Africa	57.8	63.1	49.4	72.1	49.4
74 th (2)	Botswana	55.5	69.6	47.5	59.6	40.0
76 th (3)	Mali	54.5	43.7	64.5	61.1	49.4
82 nd (4)	Ghana	52.0	60.0	48.6	58.2	37.3
85 th (5)	Burkina Faso	48.1	42.0	55.6	48.2	45.5
86 th (6)	Côte d'Ivoire	48.0	45.5	53.6	42.3	48.2
86 th (7)	Tanzania	48.0	39.7	57.4	50.6	43.5
88 th (8)	Niger	47.6	37.1	52.6	51.7	53.4
89 th (9)	Senegal	47.4	44.4	47.7	55.9	43.9
90 th (10)	Kenya	46.8	47.6	45.6	54.8	39.7
92 nd (11)	Cameroon	45.5	45.5	42.4	51.6	45.3
93 rd (12)	Benin	45.2	42.1	50.7	48.2	37.8
94 th (13)	Togo	44.2	40.8	46.7	35.1	55.1
95 th (14)	Uganda	43.9	41.5	38.0	49.2	53.7
96 th (15)	Guinea	43.0	32.5	53.1	40.4	46.4
97 th (16)	Nigeria	41.3	33.4	45.3	48.6	41.3
98 th (17)	Angola	41.1	32.6	42.6	48.7	45.9
99 th (18)	Chad	40.6	37.8	42.0	42.3	41.6
100 th (19)	Madagascar	40.4	36.3	41.1	39.9	47.3
101 st (20)	Rwanda	40.3	25.8	45.9	52.1	44.8

103 rd (21)	Congo (DR)	39.1	38.0	41.6	36.0	39.9
104 th (22)	Sierra Leone	38.1	34.1	32.1	36.8	58.0
105 th (23)	Zambia	38.0	29.0	40.4	42.0	46.4
108 th (24)	Ethiopia	37.6	24.5	47.5	41.6	39.4
109 th (25)	Malawi	37.3	23.6	40.9	37.1	55.9
110 th (26)	Sudan	37.1	31.8	31.6	52.4	41.4
111 th (27)	Mozambique	35.9	42.9	30.4	33.8	35.2
113 th (28)	Burundi	34.7	24.0	33.7	45.7	44.8

Source: Impact Economics.

The Global Food Security Index (GFSI) considers the issues of food affordability, availability, quality and safety, and natural resources and resilience across a set of 113 countries. The index is a dynamic quantitative and qualitative benchmarking model constructed from unique indicators that measure the drivers of food security across both developing and developed countries.

The African continent has been overburdened with the problem of food insecurity and is more complex in the Sub-Saharan regions, and estimating the level of food security has been very difficult. The Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) suggested a different method for each country in the region owing to individual countries' demographic and political situation. The common methods used in the region are the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) method for estimating calories available per capita at the national level, household income and expenditure surveys, and individual dietary intake discussed in the previous chapter.

Using available data from the World bank, 14,000 rural households across 94 locations in 17 countries of sub-Saharan Africa 37% of the households were food insecure – unable to achieve household food security even if all forms of income were converted into calories (Frelat et al., 2016). Food insecurity is an important dimension of poverty, and across these 14,000 households, it was associated with more household members, limited livestock, and land holdings, which together explained 72% of the variability in food availability. Market access and off-farm employment were also important (Frelat et al., 2016). Even within a single locality, there is huge diversity in food insecurity among households: Wichern et al. (2018) found as much diversity in food insecurity in each region of Nigeria as across the whole of the country. This suggests that food insecurity is everywhere, meaning that targeting cannot be restricted to particular regions.

Further, poor farmers often have the poorest soil (Giller et al., 2011, Franke et al., 2019), so small farms and poor soils become double poverty traps.

Understanding of food security in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) has been hampered by limitations in the temporal and spatial representativeness of data. Food balance sheets provide scalable estimates of per capita food availability but fail to represent food access, stability, and their causal linkages. In contrast, rural household surveys represent detailed conditions for one or multiple points in time, but are influenced by survey timing and are often limited in geographical coverage. This study draws on a large sample of rural land-holding households in SSA.

From an agronomic perspective, poor soil fertility is the primary factor that limits agricultural productivity in sub-Saharan Africa (Sanchez, 2002; Sanchez and Swaminathan, 2005). Even in the dry savannas of the Sahel, agricultural productivity is nutrient-limited (Penning de Vries and Ditéye, 1991). The critical shortages of nutrients within African farming systems indicate that mineral fertilizers are needed (Buresh et al., 1997, Giller et al., 1997). Equally, it is recognized that the management of soils solely using mineral fertilizers without attention to maintaining soil organic matter cannot sustain crop production. This has led to the paradigm of integrated soil fertility management (ISFM) (Vanlauwe et al., 2010) that recognizes the need for efficient nutrient recycling and use of crop residues and organic manures together with judicious use of mineral fertilizers. ISFM further recognizes that good crop varieties and agronomic management are essential to use nutrients and increase productivity efficiently. Intercropping and rotations with grain legumes are a key components within ISFM, enabling the capture of atmospheric nitrogen through their symbiosis with rhizobia (Giller, 2001; Vanlauwe et al., 2019). Legumes additionally provide the ability for each diversification of cropping structures and intensification, giving greater advantages in terms of human nutrition, suppression of pests and sicknesses and enhancing yields of other crops in rotations (Franke et al., 2018). Technically, the agronomists have carried out their task and realize how to close yield gaps – this has been established oftentimes in farmers' fields throughout SSA. But the terrible institutional environment, coupled with land constraints which I consider under, conspire to make an investment of price range and labor in agricultural manufacturing a much less appealing choice for smallholder farmers than looking for different varieties of income.

Smallholder farms predominate throughout sub-Saharan Africa and produce the vast majority of the food (Dixon et al., 2001). Farming systems are highly diverse, reflecting climate, soil and

cultural preferences. In many places, high population density, with concomitant pressure on land leads to small farms, and low capital availability (Jayne et al., 2014a; Muyanga and Jayne, 2014). Using data from 13,000 rural households across 93 locations in 17 countries of sub-Saharan Africa we found that a staggering 37% of the households were food insecure – unable to achieve household food security even if all forms of income were converted into calories (Frelat et al., 2016). Food insecurity is an important dimension of poverty, and across these 13,000 households it was associated with more household members, limited livestock and land holdings, which together explained 72% of the variability in food availability. Market access and off-farm employment were also important (Frelat et al., 2016). Even within a single locality there is a huge diversity in food insecurity among households: Wichern et al. (2018) found as much diversity in food insecurity in each region of Uganda as across the whole of the country. This suggests that food insecurity is everywhere, meaning that targeting cannot be restricted to particular regions. Further, poor farmers often have the poorest soils (Giller et al., 2011; Franke et al., 2019) – so small farms and poor soils become double poverty traps.

4.2. Data Research and Analysis

The aim of this research study is to evaluate the level of food security in Sub-Saharan Africa and to ascertain the individual and household dietary intake in the regions. The procedure includes a collection of individual and households data via the use of online questionnaires. A total of 100 adults completed the online survey, 79% were male and 21% female, their age bracket was between 20-70yrs and the majority of those who responded were from Nigeria, Ghana, Cameroun, and Ivory Coast. Based on the online survey age bracket are: below 20< (3%), 21- 30 (41.4%), 31- 40 (38.4%), 41- 50 (15.2%) and 51- 60 (2%)

Table 11: Socio-demographic of Investigated Individuals

Variables	Response Categories	Number (%age)
Age (Years)	<20	3 (3%)
	21-30	41 (41.4%)
	31-40	38 (38.4%)
	41-50	15 (15.2%)
	51-60	2 (2.2%)

Gender	Male	79 (79%)
	Female	21 (21%)
Education	Primary	1 (1%)
	Secondary	7 (7%)
	Tertiary	94 (94%)
Occupation	Civil Servant	18 (18%)
	Trader	5 (5%)
	Apprentice	2 (2%)
	Student	29 (29%)
	Other	49 (49%)
Household Size	<3	21 (21.2%)
	3-5	46 (46.5%)
	6-8	27 (27.3%)
	>9	5 (5.1%)

Source: own research.

In figure 26, the social demographic of the respondents, the total number of 100 individuals (male 79% and female 21%) responded, their age bracket is between 20 to 60yrs. 3% of respondents were below 20, 41 % were between the ages of 21-30, 38 % were between the ages of 31-40, 15 % were between the age bracket 41-50 and 2 % fell between the age 51-60. In education, 1 % attended primary, 7 % secondary, and a whopping 94 % attended tertiary. On occupation, 18 % were civil servants, 5 % were traders, 2 % were apprentices, 29 % were students, and 49 % were others. On household size, 21 % were <3, 46 % were 3-5 family, 27 % were 6-8, and 5 % were >9 families.

Table 12: Food Insecurity Experience Scale

Research Question	Responses	%
Worried you would not have enough food to eat because of lack of money or other resources	Yes	56%
	No	44%
Unable to eat healthy and nutritious food because of lack of money and other resources	Yes	58%
	No	42%
You ate only a few kinds of foods because of lack of money or other resources	Yes	67%
	No	33%
You had to skip a meal because there was not enough money or other resources to get food?	Yes	59%
	No	41%
You ate less than you thought you should because of lack of money or other resources	Yes	54%
	No	46%
Your household ran out of food because of a lack of money or other resources	Yes	47%
	No	55%
You were hungry but did not eat because there was not enough money or other resources?	Yes	45%
	No	55%
You went without eating for a whole day because of lack of money or other resources	Yes	18%
	No	64%
	May be	18%

Source: own research.

In figure 27, the food and insecurity scale, 56% of respondents said they were worried because they had enough food to eat due to lack of money. 58% were unable to eat healthy and nutritious food because of lack of money and other resources, 67% ate only a few kinds of foods because of lack of money or other resources, 59 % had to skip a meal because there was not enough money or other resources to get food, 54 % ate less than what they thought they should because of lack of money or other resources, 47 % of households ran out of food because of a lack of money or other resources, 45 % were hungry but did not eat because there was not enough money or other

resources and 18 % went without eating for a whole day because of lack of money or other resources.

Table 13: Households Dietary Intake Survey

Question	Response	%
Considering basic daily food requirements as the minimum food intake required for life; do you think that the basic daily food intake of your household has improved	Yes	65.3%
	No	34.7%
If 'yes' to what extent	Slightly better	45.9%
	Better	29.7%
	Much better	24.3%
If not, then	Same	80%
	Worse	18%
	Much worse	4%
Did you or other households ever skip a meal because there was not enough money for food over the last 12 months	Once a week	30.3%
	Once in 3weeks	3%
	Once in 6weeks	5.1%
	Never skipped	40.4%
	Don't know	23.2%
Did any of your children ever not eat for a whole day because of lack of money to buy food	Once a week	9.3%
	Once a month	2.1%
	Once in 3 months	1%
	Once in 6months	0%
	Never	81%
	Don't know	6.2%
I worried whether our food would run out before we got money to buy more: what was the frequency of the situation	Once a week	25.5%
	Once a month	17.3%
	Once in 3 months	9.2%
	Once in 3 months	7.1%

	Never	33.7%
	Don't know	10.2%
Did you or other household members ever eat less than you or would they have needed to eat	Once a week	29.9%
	Once a month	11.3%
	Once in 3 months	6.2%
	Once in 3 months	2.1%
	Never	34%
	Don't know	18.6%
Did any of your household members lose weight because of not having enough to eat in the past 12 months, did you lose weight due to not having enough food	Yes	25.5%
	No	59.2%
	Maybe	15.3%
Did you ever cut the size of your children's meal due to not having enough food available	Once a week	27.8%
	Once a month	6.2%
	Once in 3 months	3.1%
	Once in 3 months	2.1%
	Never	50.5%
	Don't know	10.3%
Do you consider the Saharan region to be food insecure	Yes	43.9%
	No	22.4%
	Maybe	35.7%
Do you consider your country of origin to be food secure?	Yes	15.2%
	No	54.5%
	Maybe	30.3%
Do you think that 60% of the Saharan regions are still without food?	Yes	43.9%
	No	7.1%
	Maybe	51%

Source: Own research.

In figure 28, the household dietary intake survey, a total of 65% said the daily intake of energy has improved, 30% of households skip a meal once a week because there was not enough money for food over the last 12 months, 9 % of your children did not eat once a week because of lack of

money to buy food, 25% once a week worried whether their food would run out before they got money to buy more, 30% household members once a week eat less than what or would have needed to eat, 25.5% household members lose weight because of not having enough food to eat in the past 12 months, 27.8% cut the size of their children's meal once a week due to not having enough food available, 43% consider the Saharan region to be food insecure, 15 % considered their country of origin to be food secure, and 44 % said that 60% of the Saharan regions are still without food? The outcome of the above survey put the Sub-Saharan Africa at a higher risk of food insecurity, considering the growing population of the region. More people are likely to suffer from food deficiency and numbers of people suffering from severe undernourishment is projected to rise as well as moderate and severe food insecure people

4.3 Synthesis of the Study Findings

From the responses obtained via the food security questionnaire, the socio-demographic respondents show that 94% attended tertiary education, 7% had secondary, and just 1% attended primary school. Unemployment is very high because only 18% are civil servants, 5% are traders, 2% are apprentices, 29% are students, and 49% others. It was discovered that 37% of the household's in the Sub-Saharan regions are still food insecure, many families still go to bed without food and some only manage to eat what is available, 47% could not afford the cost of balancing diet, 59% skipped meals, and 47% ate less because of lack money, 47% of households ran out of food because of lack of money, and 67% ate few kinds of food because of lack of money or other resources. In the households' dietary intake, 34.7% of the total households respondents said their daily food consumption has not improved, 30% of the households' skipped meals over the last 12 months because there was not enough money for food, and 9.3% of the total households children stay a whole day without food, 25% of the households worried of shortage of food weekly, 25.5% of households and individuals said they lost weight due to not having enough food and 27.8% said they cut the size of meals weekly because there was not enough food.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Food insecurity has continued to rise in Africa in recent years, and conflict, climate problems, and sluggish economic downturns are the key causes. The continent is not on track to eradicate hunger by 2030 (UN SDGs September 2015 goal 2), and action is urgently required to address these key underlying determinants of food security and nutrition. Commodity-dependent countries in the Africa Sub-Saharan regions suffer frequent terms of trade shocks that threaten the food security and nutrition of greater parts of the population. In most cases, the economic slowdowns and downturns that contributed to the rising undernourishment and malnutrition in 2014 – 2018 were the results of commodity price falls. The experience of the food price shock of 2010 – 2011 shows that effective policy tools are available and that countries use them. More countries in Africa are adopting social protection programmes to address poverty and food insecurity. The case of Nigeria and Ghana shows that such programmes, if fully implemented, are also effective instruments to respond to hunger and poverty

The problem of communities' war and crisis, terrorism, banditry, boko haram in the Northeast Nigeria, Cameroun, Chad, Niger and Mali and other SSA regions where all this crisis has drastically reduced the agricultural food productions due to the insecurity of these regions. Unemployment is very high, and the study shows that only 18% of the region of SSA were employed in the civil service, 5% were businessmen and women, 2% were apprentice, 29% students and 49% others. It was also discovered that 37% of the households in the Sub-Saharan regions are still food insecure, many families still go to bed without food and some only managed to eat what is available, 47% could not afford the cost of balancing diet, 59% skipped meals and 47% ate less because of lack money, 47% of households ran out of food because of lack of money and 67% ate few kinds of food because of lack of money or other resources. In the household's dietary intake, 34.7% of the total households respondents said the daily food consumption has not improved, 30% of the households' skipped meals over the last 12 months because there was not enough money for food, 9.3% of the total households More countries in the Sub-Saharan must develop policies and invest to achieve a more diversified economy and achieve an inclusive structural transformation.

The recently ratified African Continental Free Trade Area Agreement (AfCFTA) provides new opportunities for trade and investment and is of particular importance in this regard. However,

sustained economic growth is not enough. Inequalities in income, access to basic services and assets, and social exclusion prevent many from benefitting from economic growth. At the same time, they worsen the impact of slowdown and/or downturn for large parts of the population. Reducing inequalities is essential to strengthening household resilience, laying the path to inclusive growth, reducing food insecurity, and tackling the multiple forms of malnutrition and undernourishment.

Furthermore, addressing food insecurity through building human capital and strengthening access to the use of basic services also helps to reduce inequality

Finally, addressing food insecurity in the Sub-Saharan Africa regions also requires both nutrition-specific and sensitive multi-sectoral approaches. Policies and interventions must focus on promoting nutrition-sensitive food systems (which encompass the entire range of actors and their interlink activities involved in the production, aggregation, processing, distribution, consumption and disposal of food products) that can promote and sustain healthy and diverse diets. Policymakers in various SSA regions should lay more emphasis on maternal and child malnutrition and health because they are the most vulnerable.

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